

DEVELOPING EFL LEARNER'S SPEAKING SKILLS THROUGH IMPROMPTU SPEAKING METHOD

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Abstract. *The article studies the implementation ways of Impromptu method into the classroom. It is fully proved the importance of Impromptu speech in teaching English language. The actuality of this article is the investigation of Impromptu method in the way of development of the speaking skills to provide communication in learning a foreign language and making EFL classroom more effective teaching environment as a facilitator.*

Keywords: *Impromptu speech, CLT, EFL, types of speaking, interaction, monolog, dialog, polylog, role-playing, simulations*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola og`zaki nutq ko`nikmasini rivojlantirishda Badiha usulini auditoriyaga qo`llash yo`llarini o`rganadi. Tilni o`rgatishda Badiha usulining ahamiyati to`liq tasdiqlangan. Ushbu maqolaning dolzarbligi xorijiy tilni o`rganishda muloqotni ta`minlash va EFL sinfini yanada samarali o`qitish muhitini o`qituvchi sifatida amalga oshirish uchun nutq qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish uchun Badiha usulini amaliyotta qo`llay bilishdir.*

Kalit so`zlar: *Badiha usuli, CLT, EFL, muloqot turlari, o`zaro aloqa, monolog, dialog, polelog, rolli o`yinlar, simulatsiyalar*

An impromptu speech is given with little or no preparation, yet almost always with some advance knowledge on the topic. According to Shapira, Impromptu speaking was called to speak "off the cuff" on the "spur of the moment," it was usually because the speaker was quite knowledgeable about the subject. For example, if called on to speak in class, a student might give a short impromptu speech about a topic in the assigned readings. Business meetings also use a "check in" to tell everyone else about a current project. In small informal meetings, the audience would interrupt an impromptu speech and ask questions, which helped guide the statement and the information that was presented. When campaigning, politicians sometimes respond to reporters or voters almost anywhere and at any time. (Shapira, "Recommender Systems: Introduction and Challenges", 2015)

In impromptu speech activity, the speakers should maintain the topic. To keep the speech, the speaker should organize their address. Fleming stated that impromptu speech consists of three parts which were introduction, body or content, and conclusion. The first was an introduction. It was used to get attention from the audience. In the opening, the speaker started to tell their intention or what is going to talk. The speakers could also begin with a question to maintain the conversation. The second was body or content. In this case, the point could be linked logically. Besides, it could support the students in giving the argument. The last was a conclusion. The speakers should make an impression in their speech. The speakers could end the statement by providing the quotes and then said thank you to the audiences. [Fleming, "They Almost Become the Teacher", 2019] Beare also added that a speech should have an introduction, a main idea or point, supporting evidence and conclusion. (Beare, 2021)

a. Introduction

Before giving a speech, the speaker should give an introduction. Dugdale stated that in introduction, there were some aspects to be spoken. The aspects were welcoming statements and self-introduction. Welcoming statements might be various, for example "good morning, good

afternoon, good evening” [Dugdale, 2021]. After giving a welcoming statement, the speakers could give a brief self-introduction.

b. A main idea or point

In giving the speech, the speakers should have the outline of idea or topics to be explained. However, the impromptu speech speakers did not have many times to prepare it. Beare added that the speakers should put down interesting topic which would be related in some way to the event or activity they are attending. (Beare, 2021).

c. Supporting evidence

In order to provoke or giving strong statements, the speakers should give supporting evidence. When a person made a claim or presents an argument, he needed to presents evidence in support of his claim and argument in order to establish the authenticity of his claim or argument. Besides that, this method also had some disadvantages. The disadvantages of this method were: (1) The main problem of impromptu speaking was the lack of prepared statements could leave the speakers to feel embarrassed. (2) The speaker might not be able to come up with any ideas in a hurry. (3) Speech might lack detail. (4) The speaker was given little or no time to contemplate the topic. There were many kinds of strategies in teaching speaking. One of the policies was using impromptu speech. This strategy required the students to speak spontaneously without preparation and taking notes. Using the impromptu speech method could develop students speaking ability more specifically in the speaking class. Many researchers had found that delivering an impromptu speech was not an easy case. Moreover, if in the public speaking or speech in front of the people. As we already knew that the students should speak spontaneously without preparation and without taking notes. In the other hand we could say when they wanted to talk, they must pay attention to two things: how they thought about the topic and how they spoke about the issue. Jeng found that impromptu speech was perhaps the most challenging form of public speaking. Students should have appropriate time to practice speaking using the target language with an expectation that they would have experience in it [Jeng, 2021] with the purpose that when arriving at the class, they were ready to deliver the speech. However, they were still some obstacles to practicing impromptu speech outside the level.

The implementation of impromptu speaking method could improve students speaking skill especially in topic elaboration. The students would be able to elaborate more topics because the students have to speak spontaneously. Impromptu speaking method also forced someone or students to put something that speakers already knew instantly. According to Boundless, when practicing the impromptu speech, the speakers generally in control of the contents they were presenting, so they could include the topics that they wanted to talk. [Boundless, 2021] Additionally, the speakers could use personal examples from experience to support what they were saying. Since the speakers were the authority over the topic, they could speak with conviction. Delivery the speech with naturally be more conversational and spontaneous.

There were four techniques to delivering a better impromptu speech; (1) Gave yourself time to prepare and took a deep breath. In this situation made yourself feel comfortable and then stroll to the podium, used this time to collect and decide on the purpose and plan of the topics to be delivered. Before you started it, think about the opening sentences and did not have to start the speech immediately. (2) Feel confident, made yourself felt comfortable and did not deliver the speech quickly, because it could make you lack of speaking. Look at the audience and do not forget to smile at them and speak in a confident manner. (3) Slowly delivery, in this part gave your time to think ahead. Speak slowly and it allowed the audiences pay attention to the topic clearly. Also

the audiences had time to react to what you were saying. (4) Focus, this was the most important part in delivering the speech. Talk directly to the audiences and adapted to their feedback, did not be fooled by things that make you lose the focus of your speech. Making eye contacted with the audiences was important when deliver the speech and made the audiences paid attention to you. Keep the focus on the topics or subject while you deliver the speech. The four techniques above were essential while speaking in public to make the audience understand and believe the speaker's sentences. Also made the audience felt comfortable with the speakers. Steps and Instructional Teacher - Centered Learning Teacher-Centered Lecture Teacher took an active role and presents information to the entire class while the students' main role is to listen to the new information being provided. Recitation The classroom interaction followed the specific pattern of teacher initiates a question, student responds and teacher evaluates the response.

Drill and Practice

The teacher provided a series of independent tasks to reinforce a concept Demonstration The teacher helped the child's learning by showing him or her how to use materials and special tools, or how to accomplish a particular task Discussion Conversation designed to stimulate students to respond divergently and at higher cognitive levels to what they had been learning.

Cooperative Group

Small group worked that features positive interdependence, individual accountability and collaboration skills.

Guided Discovery

The teacher structured an experience or problem for students and provided a series of steps for students to follow to discover the principle, rule or generalization

Contracts

The teacher and student formed a written agreement about what work would be completed and when.

Role Play

Students acted out real life dilemmas or decisions to solve problems

Projects

An investigation was undertaken by a student or group of students to learn more about a topic

Inquiry

An instructional strategy where the teaching began with questions and relies on them heavily thereafter as ways to stimulate student exploration, discovery and critical thinking about subject matter

Self-assessment

The student had responsibility for evaluating his or her own work as a means of learning Student- Centered.

For most people, the ability to speak a foreign language is synonymous with knowing that language because speech is for them the basic means of human communication. English learners no longer expect the traditional approach of their teachers based on developing mainly the grammatical competence and using methodology popular in the past. Today, teachers are expected to provide their students with useful active knowledge of the foreign language, not just theory about the language. The area I focused on, were communicative activities and their categorization: interview activities, discussions, role plays, simulations and guessing games.

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